

Design of miniaturized dual-band bandpass filter with enhanced selectivity for GPS and RFID applications

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a miniaturized interdigital coupled dual-band bandpass filter with multiple transmission zeros/poles. Stepped impedance resonators, interdigital coupled lines, and series coupled lines make up the proposed filter design. A circuit simulator is used to analyze a proposed filter, and the magnitude and bandwidth shifts have been investigated. To confirm the proposed filter design, equations for transmission zero frequencies have been constructed and verified based on even-odd mode analysis and lossless transmission line theory. A working prototype for 2.2 GHz (RFID) and 1.38 GHz (GPS) applications is made and tested. With λ_g representing the guided wavelength at the first band (1.38GHz), the finished prototype is compact, measuring $0.32 \lambda_g \times 0.27 \lambda_g$. According to the experimental findings, there is strong selectivity in the first and second passbands, with roll-off rates of 190 and 168 dB/GHz, respectively. Good isolation between the two passbands is indicated by an insertion loss of less than 20 dB.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of modern wireless communication systems, the demand for efficient and versatile bandpass filters has surged, driven by the need for enhanced signal quality and spectrum utilization. Among the various filter designs, dual-band microstrip bandpass filters have garnered significant attention due to their compact size, ease of integration, and ability to operate across multiple frequency bands simultaneously. By leveraging advanced electromagnetic modeling techniques and innovative substrate materials, these filters offer superior performance characteristics such as improved bandwidth, higher selectivity, and lower insertion loss. Such attributes are crucial for enhancing the efficiency and reliability of communication systems in applications ranging from satellite communications and radar systems to wireless sensor networks and medical telemetry.

The literature introduces the design of a microstrip dual-band bandpass filter with closely specified passbands [1]-[4]. Precise control over the passband frequencies and bandwidths is achieved through meticulous design and optimization of the microstrip layout. A high selectivity compact dual-band bandpass filter with seven transmission-zeros designed for GPS and WiMAX applications is discussed in the literature [5], [6].

The use of multiple transmission-zeros enhances the filter's selectivity and out-of-band rejection, ensuring high performance in demanding environments. This design approach provides a robust solution for dual-band operation in critical communication applications. Research investigates both single- and dual-band bandpass filters employing coupled stepped-impedance resonators with embedded coupled-lines [7]. This approach achieves enhanced coupling and improved filter performance. An article presents a dual-band high-temperature superconducting hairpin-resonator bandpass filter that operates based on two pairs of nondegenerate modes [8]. The use of high-temperature superconducting materials significantly reduces losses, resulting in higher quality factors and better filter performance. The design of dual-band interdigital bandpass filters utilizing both series and shunt resonators was studied [9], [10]. The combination of these resonators enables the creation of filters with precise control over the passbands and transmission zeros, resulting in high-performance filters with improved out-of-band rejection.

A study introduces a high-selectivity tunable dual-band bandpass filter using stub-loaded stepped-impedance resonators [11]. This configuration provides flexibility in achieving narrowband and wideband responses, making it ideal for various wireless communication applications. The design of an on-chip dual-band bandpass filter using lumped elements in low-temperature co-fired ceramic (LTCC) technology was studied [12], [13]. The integration of lumped elements on-chip allows for miniaturization and compatibility with monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMICs). A compact lowpass and dual-band bandpass filter with controllable transmission zeros, center frequencies, and passband bandwidth was analyzed [14]. The compact size and controllable characteristics make this filter an attractive option for multifunctional communication systems. The use of varactor diodes allows for real-time tuning of the filter's center frequencies, making it adaptable to varying operational requirements [15]. The literature introduces a dual-band balanced bandpass filter utilizing slot lines loaded patch resonators, enabling independent control of bandwidths for each passband [16]. The innovative design allows for precise adjustments of resonant frequencies and bandwidths, providing high flexibility in filter applications.

A dual-band balanced bandpass filter developed using electrically small planar resonators features excellent common-mode suppression, critical for maintaining signal integrity in differential signaling environments [17]. The compact size of the resonators and efficient suppression of common-mode noise make this filter suitable for high-density electronic circuits and systems. The design of dual-band bandpass filters based on metal-integrated suspended line technology is studied in this article [18]. The use of suspended lines offers low insertion loss and high-quality factors, enhancing overall filter performance. This work presents a bandpass filter that can be tuned across a wide frequency range while maintaining high selectivity [19]. The proposed design focuses on improving frequency selectivity and achieving a wide tuning range, which is significant for applications requiring versatile frequency management. It utilizes frequency-dependent S-L (series-to-line) coupling to achieve high selectivity and compact size, making it suitable for applications with stringent size and performance requirements [20].

This article describes a tunable bandpass filter covering a frequency range from 0.86 to 3.83 GHz [21]. The filter is designed to offer high selectivity across its entire tuning range, which is beneficial for radio frequency (RF) and microwave applications requiring precise frequency filtering. The paper presents a dual-band bandpass filter with constant absolute bandwidth and reconfigurable bandwidth capability [22]-[24]. The filter utilizes a mode control technique to adjust bandwidth, making it versatile for applications needing adjustable dual-band operation. This research introduces a bandpass filter that can intrinsically switch between constant absolute bandwidth (CABW) and constant fractional bandwidth (CFBW) modes [25]. The filter's design allows for flexible bandwidth management and is suitable for diverse electronic applications requiring adaptable filtering characteristics. In the recently reported literature has low selectivity in passband to stop band or stop band to stop band. Therefore, in this proposed work address all these issues.

This brief proposes a miniaturized second order interdigital line loaded dual band pass filter which generates two transmission poles in each passband and five transmission zeros in the stopband. The proposed filter has enhanced skirt rate due to the presence of multiple transmission zeros/poles. In the presented filter consists of two set of interdigital coupled lines and meandering open stubs and two feeding ports. The fabricated and experimentally validated filter layout is etched on Rogers RT/Duriod 5880 substrate. The fabricated filter's filtering characteristics are matched with the simulated and theoretical response.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Figures 1 and 2, Figures 1(a) and (b) show the proposed dual band bandpass filter's layout and transmission line design, respectively. A shunt-coupled line ($1/Y_{E1}$, $1/Y_{O1}, \theta$), loaded with a pair of open stubs ($1/Y_3, \theta$), two series-coupled lines ($1/Y_{E2}$, $1/Y_{O2}, \theta$), and stepped-impedance open-stubs ($1/Y_1, \theta$) and ($1/Y_2, \theta$) make up this arrangement. An Ansys HFSS 2024R1 is used to simulate the suggested filter setup, and the equivalent circuit is presented in Figure 1(c). Two passbands, with a return loss of more than 22 dB in

each, are present in the circuit-simulated response, which is centered at 1.38 and 2.2 GHz. In addition, this filter has five transmission zeros (TZs) in the stopband and two transmission poles (TPs) in each passband. The presented filter setup is investigated using a lossless transmission line model method. The designed filter’s optimized physical dimensions are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 1. The dual band bandpass filter: (a) structure top view, (b) bottom view, and (c) equivalent circuit analysis

Table 1. The presented dual-band pass filter physical dimension

Parameter	Value (Mm)	Parameter	Value (Mm)	Parameter	Value (Mm)	Parameter	Value (Mm)	Parameter	Value (Mm)
P	33	L ₂	13	L ₅	12	L ₈	1.75	L ₁₁	7
G	35	L ₃	3	L ₆	1.25	L ₉	3.25	W ₁	2
L ₁	12	L ₄	10	L ₇	0.75	L ₁₀	2		

A band stop response with three TZs (fTZ3, fTZ4, and fTZ5) is produced by the cascaded section of shunt coupled line and parallel open stubs when the impedance values are appropriately chosen [21]. A wide passband response is offered by the open circuited stub transmission lines. The combination of the band stop section and series linked lines truncates this wide passband response into two narrow passbands. Furthermore, TZs (fTZ2, fTZ6) are inserted in the lower and higher stop bands by using stepped impedance open-stubs in order to increase the selectivity on the lower and upper sides of the passband. Researcher [17]-[21], the selectivity is not enhanced in both the stop band to pass band and pass band to stop band. 1/Y1 and 1/Y2 impedances controls the TZ positions [22]. Even-odd mode analysis is used to validate the filter's TZ frequencies while the proposed filter construction is symmetric. The even and odd transmission line models are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), respectively. These are the even and odd mode input impedances that are determined using the loss free transmission line theory [23]. The total admittance variation of the filter is derived with the help of equivalent circuit model and it is given in (1) to (12).

$$\frac{1}{y_{inE}} = \frac{1}{\frac{Y_{SIS}Y_{CE}}{Y_{SIS} + \frac{1}{Y_{CE}}}} \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{1}{y_{inO}} = \frac{\frac{1}{Y_{SIS}Y_{CO}}}{\frac{1}{Y_{SIS}} + \frac{1}{Y_{CO}}} \tag{2}$$

Where,

$$\frac{1}{Y_{CE}} = -jA_{C1} \cot \theta + \frac{\frac{1}{Y_{C2}^2} \text{csc}^2 \theta}{\frac{1}{Y_{PE} + jY_{C1}} \cot \theta} \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{CO}} = -jA_{C1} \cot \theta + \frac{\frac{1}{Y_{C2}^2} \text{csc}^2 \theta}{\frac{1}{Y_{PO} + jY_{C1}} \cot \theta} \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{C1}} = \frac{\frac{1}{Y_{E1}} + \frac{1}{Y_{O1}}}{2} \tag{5a}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{C2}} = \frac{\frac{1}{Y_{E1}} - \frac{1}{Y_{O1}}}{2} \tag{5b}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{PE}} = \frac{1}{Y_{E2}} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{Y_{OC1}} - \frac{1}{jY_{E2} \tan \theta}}{\frac{1}{Y_{E2}} - \frac{1}{jY_{OC2} \tan \theta}} \right] \tag{5c}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{OC1}} = \frac{1}{-jY_3 \cot \theta} \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{PO}} = \frac{1}{-jY_{O2} \tan \theta} \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{1}{Y_{AIS}} = \frac{1}{jY_1} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{Y_1} \tan \theta - \frac{1}{Y_2 \cot \theta}}{\frac{1}{Y_1} + \frac{1}{Y_2}} \right] \tag{8}$$

It is possible to define the S-parameters of the recommended dual bandpass filter in terms of even and odd mode admittances as,

$$S_{11} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{Z_0}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1}{Z_{inE}Z_{inO}}\right)}{\left(\frac{1}{Z_0} + \frac{1}{Z_{inE}}\right)\left(\frac{1}{Z_0} + \frac{1}{Z_{inO}}\right)} \tag{9a}$$

$$S_{11} = \frac{\frac{1}{Z_0}\left(\frac{1}{Z_{inE}}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{Z_{inO}}\right)}{\left(\frac{1}{Z_0} + \frac{1}{Z_{inE}}\right)\left(\frac{1}{Z_0} + \frac{1}{Z_{inO}}\right)} \tag{9b}$$

by setting $S_{21}=0$, the circuit-simulated TZ frequencies of the suggested filter may be confirmed, yielding,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{Y_{SIS}} \left(\frac{1}{Y_{CE}} - \frac{1}{Y_{CO}} \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{1}{Y_{SIS}} = 0 \text{ and } \frac{1}{Y_{CE}} - \frac{1}{Y_{CO}} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{10a}$$

simplifying $\frac{1}{Y_{SIS}} = 0$, we get,

$$\theta = \theta_{TZ2} = \cot^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{Y_2}{Y_1}} \right) \tag{10b}$$

simplifying $\frac{1}{Y_{CE}} = \frac{1}{Y_{CO}}$, we get,

$$\tan^2\theta \left(\frac{1}{Y_{E2}Y_{O2}} + \frac{1}{Y_3Y_{O2}} - \left(\frac{1}{Y_{E2}} \right)^2 \right) = \frac{-1}{Y_{E2}Y_3} \quad (11a)$$

$$\theta = \theta_{TZ3} = \tan^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\frac{-1}{Y_{E2}Y_3}}{\frac{1}{Y_{E2}Y_{O2}} + \frac{1}{Y_3Y_{O2}} - \left(\frac{-1}{Y_{E2}} \right)^2}} \right) \quad (11b)$$

The TZ frequencies may be found using (9) based on the link between electrical length and design frequency.

$$f_{TZn} = \frac{\theta_{TZn}}{\theta_0} f_0 (n = 2,3,5,6) \quad (12)$$

Figure 2. The presented dual band pass filter equivalent circuit (a) even mode and (b) odd mode

The series connected lines' intrinsic zeros are the TZs at $f_{TZ1}=0$ and $f_{TZ7}=2f_0$ [18]. The f_{TZ2} and f_{TZ3} may be derived from (7)–(10). Since the response is symmetric, $2f_0 - f_{TZ3}$ and $2f_0 - f_{TZ2}$, respectively, can provide f_{TZ5} and f_{TZ6} . In (7), the denominator and numerator reach infinity at the same time when $\theta=90^\circ$ ($f_0=1$ GHz). But the higher-order denominator gets closer to infinity first, creating a TZ at f_{TZ4} . The computed seven TZ frequencies are 0.5, 0.91, 1.89, 2.05, and 2.59 GHz, and they are perfectly complement with the circuit simulated ones proving the proposed filter structure. Having into consideration $1/Y_{E1}=190$, $1/Y_{O1}=85$, $1/Y_{E2}=132$, $1/Y_{O2}=77$, $1/Y_1=130$, $1/Y_2=78$, $1/Y_3=110$, $\theta=90$, and $f_0=1$ GHz.

Varying the impedances ($1/Y_1$, $1/Y_2$, $1/Y_3$) and coupling coefficients ($K_1=(1/Y_{E1}-1/Y_{O1})/(1/Y_{E1}+1/Y_{O1})$ and $K_2=(1/Y_{E2}-1/Y_{O2})/(1/Y_{E2}+1/Y_{O2})$) of the proposed dual band bandpass filter allows to study the magnitude response of the circuit simulation. The return loss in both passbands increases when $1/Y_1$ and $1/Y_2$ decreases. $1/Y_3$ enhances the passbands' return loss and improves the inter-stopband's rejection level. As K_1 increases, so does the distance between the pass bands. An increase in K_2 improves the inter-stopband responsiveness. This research suggests that by appropriately choosing the impedances of the proposed structure, it is possible to regulate the centre frequencies of two passbands with good matching. The change of the pass bands' 3 dB FBWs for various values of the presented dual band bandpass filter is shown in Figure 3. There is less variability in the 3-dB FBWs as $1/Y_1$ and $1/Y_2$ increases. While it lowers as K_2 grows, the 3 dB FBWs of both passbands increase when $1/Y_3$ and K_1 increase as shown in Figures 3(a) to 3(e).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, it is explained the results of research and at the same time is given the comprehensive discussion. Section 2 analysis and the design process described in [24] led to the finalized values of $1/Y_{E1}=190$, $1/Y_{O1}=75$, $1/Y_{E2}=121$, $1/Y_{O2}=55$, $1/Y_1=140$, $1/Y_2=92$, $1/Y_3=120$, $\theta=90^\circ$, and $f_0=2.4$ GHz for the circuit implementation. The develop and simulate the proposed dual band bandpass filter using Ansys HFSS V 2014R1 full-wave EM simulator. For the construction of the presented filter, Rogers RT/Duriod 5880 substrate with a dielectric constant of 2.2, a thickness of 0.78 mm, and a loss tangent of 0.0009 is employed. The comparison of simulated and measured S-parameter responses and fabricated pictures are plotted in Figure 4. From Figure 4, both the bands return loss are enhanced compared with the all other dual band pass filter responses.

Figure 3. Lower and upper band filter's 3 dB-FBW variation: (a) $1/Y_1$, (b) $1/Y_2$, (c) $1/Y_3$, (d) K_1 , and (e) K_2

Figure 4. Simulated and measured S-parameter response

A vector network analyzer is used to assess the group latency and magnitude responses of the proposed dual band bandpass filter. The two passbands with frequencies centred at 1.35 GHz and 2.2 GHz had their tested 3 dB FBWs determined to be 14.33% and 6.59%, respectively. At 1.35 and 2.2 GHz, the observed insertion losses are 1.2 dB and 1.1 dB, respectively. In the first passband, the measured return losses are 21 dB, and in the second passband, they are 19.8 dB. The simulated and measured group delay is illustrated in Figure 5.

The first band's tested roll-off rate is 190 dB/GHz, while the second band's is 168 dB/GHz. These results are more precise than the ones found in [2], [7], [9], [11], [12], [15], [17]. Figure 5(b) shows the measured group delay of the presented dual band bandpass filter. Group delay ranges from 2.1 to 5.2 ns in the first passband and from 2.4 to 6.6 ns in the second. The simulated and measured values varied somewhat because of measurement uncertainties and manufacturing tolerances. The simulated and measured group delay is illustrated in Figures 5(a) and 5(b).

Table 2 presents a comparison of the proposed dual band bandpass filter's performance with previous reported efforts. With similar 3 dB FBWs and more transmission zeros, the recommended filter is less in size. It is possible to scale the design for various dual-band applications because it is built on a transmission line concept.

Figure 5. Simulated and measured group delay response (a) lower band and (b) upper band

Table 2. Proposed dual-band bandpass filters performance comparison with other reported filters

Reference	f_1, f_2	f_1/f_2	3-dB FBW (%)	No. of TZs	Order (N)	Size ($\lambda_g \times \lambda_g$)	Applications
[2]	2.1, 5.9	2.12	7.0/4.0	3	1	0.27×0.27	GSM, ISM
[7]	2.45, 5.45	3.22	2.4/2.3	2	2	0.33×0.42	ISM, Wi-Max
[9]	2.45, 4.3	1.50	2.22/1.70	3	3	0.72×0.34	ISM, Wi-Fi
[11]	1.9, 3.15	2.25	7.0/5.5	1	2	0.66×0.54	ISM
[12]	2.4, 5.2	2.08	10.7/5.4	4	2	0.92×0.59	-
[15]	2.2, 3.9	3.8	6.5/4.9	5	3	0.88×0.72	-
[17]	2.45, 5.1	1.49	3.3/4.6	2	2	0.58×0.67	ISM, WLAN
This work	1.35, 2.2	2.1	2.9/2.6	4	2	0.32×0.27	GPS, Wi-Max

4. CONCLUSION

Using two stepped impedance resonators, meandering open stubs and interdigital coupled line, a minimized dual-band bandpass filter is proposed and realized. Seven transmission zeros are included in the stopband of the presented filter, and its passband response is second-order. The presented filter's lower band operates at 1.34 GHz for GPS and the upper band operates at 2.2 GHz for RFID applications. Better isolation between the passbands, selectivity, and fractional bandwidth are all features of the designed filter.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Thupalli Shaik	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓
Mahammed Basha														
Arun Raaza		✓				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Vishakha Bhujbal	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	
Meena Mathivanan		✓				✓	✓	✓			✓			✓

C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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